

Climate Change & Pakistan's Coastline: **Risks and Resilience**

A comprehensive report by the Policy and Research Team,
Climate Forward Pakistan.

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ORGANISATIONAL PROFILE:

Climate Forward Pakistan (CFP) is an independent, youth-led organisation driven by the belief that young people hold the power to drive bold, people-centred climate solutions. What began as a targeted response to gaps in policy, advocacy, and representation has evolved into a comprehensive platform committed to climate justice, equity, and resilience. We recognize that youth from climate-vulnerable contexts have invaluable lived experiences and leadership potential, and we work to bridge the gap between these frontline communities and high-level decision-making spaces.

To ensure youth inclusion moves beyond mere symbolic representation, CFP focuses on policy engagement, capacity building, and community-driven advocacy. Through structured programs, mentorship, and strategic collaboration with civil society, youth networks, and institutional partners, the organisation creates concrete pathways for young people, including children, to understand, access, and meaningfully contribute to the climate agenda. Our continued engagement across national and international platforms shows a strong commitment to ensuring youth participation is informed, prepared, and truly impactful.

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FOREWORD

Pakistan's coastline is at the frontline of climate change, facing rising sea levels, erosion, and growing socio-economic threats. This report by Climate Forward Pakistan (CFP) offers a timely and insightful exploration of these risks, blending research with policy recommendations and regional case studies.

It highlights both the urgency of the climate crisis and the resilience needed to protect vulnerable communities and ecosystems. Authored by a passionate team of young researchers, this work is a call to action for policymakers, civil society, and all those committed to a sustainable coastal future.

We thank all contributors for their unwavering support in bringing this vision to life.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Pakistan's coastline along the Arabian Sea is grappling with the adverse impacts of climate change, including but not limited to rising sea levels, coastal erosion, coral bleaching, and ocean acidification. These environmental threats are endangering marine biodiversity, infrastructure, and the lives of many people who live in coastal areas, especially in Sindh and Balochistan.

This report, designed by Climate Forward Pakistan (CFP), looks into the significance of coastal areas in Pakistan and identifies the risks brought by climate change. It reviews existing policies, finds problems in governance, and examines the best strategies followed in countries like India, Bangladesh, and Maldives. The report's findings indicate that Pakistan struggles with enforcing environmental regulations, waste and water management, community engagement in scientific endeavors, and disaster preparedness. Moreover, rising sea levels threaten critical infrastructure and the success of major projects like the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC).

The report calls for immediate changes in policy, including requiring Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), stricter measures against plastic waste, supporting sustainable tourism, and increasing efforts in community conservation. It further proposes measures to make coastal areas more resilient to climate change for the sake of the environment, national safety, and the economy.

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan's extensive coastline, which spans approximately 1050 kilometers along the Arabian Sea^[1], is facing numerous impacts of climate change. It is among the top countries most susceptible to climate-induced challenges, such as sea-level rise, extreme weather events, and coastal erosion.^[2] Over recent years, a rise in the frequency and power of tropical cyclones, severe storms and floods has caused loss of life and property damage in coastal regions.^[3] Higher sea levels lead to erosion of the shore and flooding of low-elevation regions which harm habitats, infrastructure and employment opportunities. Communities dependent on fishing and agriculture are experiencing reduced yields due to changing marine ecosystems and saltwater intrusion into arable lands.

Pakistan ranked as the 38th 'most vulnerable' and 32nd 'least ready' country in the world to address climate change impacts.^[4] As recorded by the UK Met Office in 2021, in Pakistan, about one million people are expected to face flooding risks from the coast every year by 2070 if proper actions are not taken.^[5] Thus, a combination of proactive policies, enhanced coastal defences, sustainable land-use practices, and community-based resilience initiatives is required to mitigate the long-term effects of climate change on Pakistan's coastal regions.

OVERVIEW OF PAKISTAN'S COASTLINE

Pakistan boasts a 1050 km coastline and holds the 74th position among 142 countries with the most strategically advantageous maritime locations.^[6] Pakistan's coastline is divided into two sections: the Makran coast (720 km) and the Sindh coast (270 km).^[7]

Its maritime domain plays a crucial role in nation's economic and military strength, with 95% of the country's trade conducted via sea routes.^[8] Given its extensive maritime potential, Pakistan has the opportunity to expand its blue economy, harnessing marine resources for sustainable economic growth.

IMPORTANCE OF COASTAL AREAS IN NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE:

The value of Pakistan's coastal areas is mainly seen in their ports, trade routes, seafood industry and maritime tourism, among others. Pakistan's leading seaports, Karachi Port, Port Qasim and Gwadar Port, are very important for global trade and business. Most of Pakistan's imports and exports come from these ports, thus, they play a big role in the economy.^[9] However, their maximum potential is still being held back by issues such as insufficient infrastructure, political instability, and security concerns. The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is a key initiative aimed at enhancing the efficiency and capacity of these ports, fostering regional connectivity, and supporting China's maritime ambitions.^[10] Because of CPEC, Pakistan's coastline is now recognized for its strategic importance and role in world trade and regional linkages.

Many coastal communities in Balochistan and Sindh depend on the fishing industry in Pakistan for their main income. Marine fisheries contribute about 64% of total fish production.^[11] Experts say that creating better practices in Pakistan's fishing industry could allow it to reach up to \$4 billion in yearly exports.^[12] Despite its potential, the sector faces challenges such as declining fish exports and limited aquaculture development. Additionally, inadequate regulation and enforcement of sustainable fishing practices have contributed to the depletion of fish stocks, which in turn affects both economic output and biodiversity. So, supporting aquaculture, well-managed fisheries and higher-value processing of seafood could make Pakistan more competitive globally and more productive.

The coastline of Pakistan is rich in beaches and islands such as Gadani, Jiwani, Pasni, Kund Malir, Haft Talar and Astola Island which have a lot of tourism potential. The development of maritime tourism could create income of \$1-2 billion a year by highlighting yachting, scuba diving and ecotourism.^[13] This sector can create jobs, boost foreign exchange earnings, and uplift coastal communities.

CULTURAL AND SOCIAL IMPORTANCE:

Millions of Pakistanis make a living from the resources found along the coast, mainly in fishing, port activities and tourism. Building and improving local infrastructure and putting in place economic policies can help improve these communities and give them opportunities to earn. The culture of coastal areas in Pakistan includes traditional maritime activities, folk music, and seafood-based cuisine. Preserving and promoting this heritage can enhance cultural tourism and economic opportunities.

However, coastal populations often face poverty, inadequate healthcare, lack of education, and environmental challenges such as coastal erosion and pollution. Dealing with these issues using targeted development programs supports both social fairness and progress of the economy.

CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS IN PAKISTAN

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ON COASTAL AREAS:

Climate change poses growing ecological risks to coastal communities, such as rise in sea level, coastal erosion, coral bleaching, and ocean acidification.

Sea Level Rise:

The rise in the average sea level is a measure of the increase in the height of the ocean above the centre of the Earth. These sea levels are an important indicator of climate change, which has far-reaching consequences on the coastal population and the distribution of the sea. The sea level all over the world has increased by more than 10 cm between 1993 and 2024.^[14] The significant causes of the increase in sea level include:

- Thermal expansion of sea water.
- Growth and decay of land-based glaciers and ice-caps.
- Terrestrial water storage, i.e., dams, reservoirs, lakes, and ground water depletion.^[15]

The coastal regions of Pakistan, including the Indus Delta in Sindh province, are in great danger due to an increase in sea level. It is a low-lying area and hence it is very vulnerable due to low-lying terrain and a weak ecosystem. It has been measured that the rate of increase in sea level along the Karachi coast is about 1.1 mm a year, which is consistent with the global pattern.^[16] This causes people living on the coasts to experience more floods, salination of agricultural areas, and displacement, leading to adverse effects on livelihood and economy.

Thus, ongoing sea level rise along Pakistan's coast, particularly in the vulnerable Indus Delta region, poses severe risks to both the natural ecosystem and human settlements, necessitating urgent and sustained efforts in coastal management, adaptation, and policy interventions to safeguard livelihood and economic stability.

Coastal Erosion:

Along the coastlines of Pakistan, the ongoing increase in sea level, decrease in the movement of fresh water, and anthropogenic issues are causing a drastic erosion of shores and promoting the risk to coasts and infrastructure, particularly in Sindh and Balochistan. Erosion along the coast in the creation of coastal landforms has been natural throughout history. Coastal erosion and rising water levels wash away the shores, while violent storms intensify this process.

The coastal erosion has a strong influence on the coasts of Pakistan, especially in the region of Sindh and Balochistan, where natural and man-made factors contributed to the destruction of the coasts. This further worsens the erosion that is expected to continue to rise by about 1.1 mm per year, coupled with the extreme limitation of fresh water supplies through the Indus River, which as a result has been dammed and diverted to the agricultural process. The most affected regions include Karachi and Gwadar. Karachi has an average erosion rate of 2.43 meters per year.^[17] This ongoing degradation threatens the vital ecosystems, infrastructure, and local communities, highlighting the need for comprehensive coastal management.

Several districts in Pakistan are highly affected by coastal erosion, with varying degrees of severity. Which includes:

- **Thatta district:** Specifically, Kharo Chann faces severe erosion as an estuarine mudflat.
- **Badin district:** Fears severe erosion in its creek and mudflat areas.
- **Sujawal, Jati & Shah Bundeer:** All faces severe erosion in their creek and mudflat region.
- **Gwadar:** Jwani and Shadi Kor face severe erosion.
- **Lasbela:** The Dam faces severe erosion due to its dune composition.^[18]

The coastal areas of Sindh and Balochistan are generally more prone to the direct impact of sea-level rise and rising temperatures, making them vulnerable to erosion.

Coral Bleaching:

The coral reef represents one of the most aesthetic, ancient, and complicated environments on the planet. The coral reefs on the coast of Pakistan are of economic and ecological importance. Nevertheless, climate change and anthropogenic threats pose a great threat to them. Some significant reasons that have caused loss to coral reefs are the development of industries, pollution, overfishing, the effect of tourism, elevated sedimentation and change of climate. About 10% of the population of Pakistan resides at coastal region and 20% of area is moderately developed and 40%

of industry exists in this zone^[19]. Such stressors have immobilized the coral ecosystem, rendering it easily susceptible to the occurrence of bleaching. It is of note that there was an animation of a serious coral bleaching event reported near Churna Island. Which is the first recorded event of such a kind in Pakistan. As a reaction, WWF Pakistan requested the government to adopt Churna Island as a marine protected area (MPA) to reduce the impact of industries and expand on tourism and fisheries sustainability^[20]. There is a need to have proactive conservation interventions to ensure that further degradation is avoided and ensure biodiversity is in the name for future generations.

The following figure outlines the natural and human-induced (anthropogenic) threats to coral reef ecosystems, such as sea level rise and pollution, and their impacts, including biodiversity loss and reduced fish production. It also highlights multi-tiered conservation responses through management practices, legislation, and awareness efforts involving NGOs and local communities. These integrated initiatives are crucial to protect coral reefs, ensuring their resilience and enhancing the vital ecological and economic benefits they provide for future generations.

fig. Threats and Conservation Strategies for Coral Reef Ecosystems in Pakistan

Ocean Acidification:

Pakistan has a rich coastline with the Arabian Sea covering more than 1000 km, which is beautiful with brimming biodiversity and economic prospects. Nevertheless, let it not be mistaken, this beautiful coast hides the bottom number of interconnected hazards that entangle the elements of nature and people's growth. This is because there is a constant struggle to maintain these natural wonders as well as make ends meet in this region, especially due to the emerging threat of global warming.

One of the major issues that threatens the coastal water and marine life in Pakistan is ocean acidification, which occurs due to the absorption of atmospheric excess carbon dioxide (CO₂). When the ocean uses up CO₂, seawater will become acidic, and this process will affect the physiological processes of coral reefs, shellfish, as well as other calcifying organisms.^[21] Such processes render the formation and sustainability of calcium carbonate shells and skeletons of these organisms hard, which influences their development, reproduction, and survival as a whole. Therefore it is significant to solve the problem of ocean acidification to maintain the marine environment's biodiversity, sustain fisheries, and safeguard the lives of coast-based communities.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT ON COASTAL AREAS:

Climate change is subjecting the global society to socio-economic ills, such as increasing economic losses and threats to the lives of individuals living in coastal areas across the world. Some of the dreadful effects of climate change, especially the effects of human activities, are heat waves, a rise in temperature, climatic disasters, a rise in sea level, and the melting of ice sheets. There are almost 600 million people faced with the threat of rising sea levels in low-lying areas along the global coastal region. Uncontrolled coastal flooding is estimated to result in economic losses up to 14 trillion dollars a year by 2100.^[22]

Climate change is a worsening crisis in Pakistan, which is endangering Pakistan's major economic projects like the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), especially along the economically weaker Gwadar coast, reducing economic growth and development in the country. Consequently, the climate crisis poses a never-ending threat to the existing ecosystem, biodiversity, and oceans in Pakistan. In Pakistan, climate change is more significantly seen, especially on the coastlines of Balochistan, and it is feared that the effect will grow even worse as times go by. Climate change can impact the biggest initiative of Pakistan, the Gwadar Coast, entitled the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), which tends to boost the economic condition of Pakistan and GDP to a higher level with its new project of energy and global trade systems. Major socio-economic threats include:

- **Reduced marine life:** Increased ocean temperature and the acidification of the ocean pose a threat to marine life, contributing to the loss of fish stocks in the oceans, which serve as an important source of food for the coastal populations. It has been revealed that about 40-70% of the fish are already extinct, which endangers the common food source and economic security.
- **Agriculture damage:** The fertile soil is contaminated with seawater that enters the land because of high levels of sea and thus becomes nonresponsive to agricultural particles. Hundreds of acres of productive agricultural land lying in the Badin area have become unusable due to this problem.
- **Displacement of communities:** The effect of rapid climate change, such as an increase in sea level, may displace communities located in endangered ecological areas, which will result in strain on resources and food supply.
- **Impact on infrastructure:** Infrastructure in Pakistan is under threat of coastal erosion caused by sea level rise. There is a threat of damage or destruction to the residential building, roads, ports, and other critical facilities. Flooding of the coastal zones and higher intensity of storms and storm surges may cause the collapse of infrastructure, including transportation systems, utilities, and services. The infrastructure damage interrupts the daily activities and results in substantial economic losses to make the repairs needed to rebuild it. These studies highlighted the susceptibility of Pakistani coastal building infrastructure and the necessity to respond to it with adaptation measures.

These challenges collectively underscore the urgent need for comprehensive adaptation strategies to safeguard Pakistan's coastal communities and economic stability in the face of escalating climate risk.

SECURITY RISKS POSED BY CLIMATE CHANGE TO COASTAL AREAS:

Climate change poses a major risk to the coastal region of Pakistan since it has created challenges with regard to resources and economic sustainability. It is shown that sea level and temperature shall continue to increase, with the possibility of an increase of 10 cm of sea level in Karachi coastal regions, which endangers the resources and population.^[23] The changes compound the current threats and causes of instability that add security concerns with food, water, and energy.

The negative effect of the decreases in fisheries resources in the coastal region, such as Gwadar, due to the changing weather patterns is directly on the livelihood and food security, which is adding to the financial burden and may lead to social tension. Highly salty water, together with flooding caused by rising sea levels, worsens the quality of agriculture, land, and water resources, which further compromises food security and economic stability.^[24] A combination of factors increases the threats of displacement, migration, and rivalry over secure resources, which can result in conflict and instability.

POLICY EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

REVIEW OF PAKISTAN'S EXISTING COASTAL MANAGEMENT AND CLIMATE POLICIES:

The Government of Pakistan launched the "Blue Carbon" project in 2020 with the aim of estimating the potential carbon stock of the country's coastal ecosystems, specifically the mangrove forests, as these biomes are essential for carbon sequestration. Tragically, the coastal regions of Pakistan are under severe stress from natural disasters like cyclones, storms, floods, and erosion.

The following protective measures have been decided to be taken by the Government of Pakistan to respond these challenges according to the National Climate Change Policy:

1

Ensuring the construction of natural barriers, which includes planting and regeneration of mangroves, serves as a natural protector. Additionally, the government is also promoting the planting of coastal palms and other native tree species to strengthen the coastal ecosystem, which assists in securing the coast. These green barriers will reduce the impact of cyclones and tsunamis along with supporting biodiversity and the local population.

2

Construction of barriers near low-lying human settlements to protect from rising sea levels and cyclones.

3

Development of salinity-tolerant crop species for agriculture in coastal areas.

4

Maintenance of optimal river water flow so that sediments and nutrients can reach coastal areas.

5

Collaboration and partnership with the ministry of maritime affairs to exploit and tap the potential of the Blue Economy.

6

Reducing and controlling both solid and liquid pollution.

- 7 Assessing the threats to the fishing sector and coming up with strategies to promote aquaculture.
- 8 Optimizing the fisheries sector by taking care of the habitat for fish.
- 9 Capacity building of local coastal communities.
- 10 Capacity building of fishermen cooperative societies.
- 11 Sustain tourism opportunities and diversify livelihood opportunities to prevent inland migration and movements.

The NCCP5 has defined all the policy measures mentioned above. Pakistan is somewhat on the track when it comes to policy formulation, but a lot is still left, and there is still room for improvement.

Identification of policy gaps and weaknesses:

- 1 Development projects in Pakistan proceed without an environmental impact assessment that leads to ecosystem degradation.
- 2 Citizen science is still an underdeveloped and unfamiliar concept in Pakistan.
- 3 Although the government has banned the use of plastic, the implementation of regulations is ineffective.

Recommendations for improved coastal governance, resilience, and adaptation strategies:

- 1 A proper environmental impact assessment must be done before initiating any project. The figure below explains the steps to EIA. It consists of initiating an idea for a new project, then decision-making to go for an EIA, then starting of the EIA, then reporting, and finally deciding whether the project should be initiated or not.

2

Citizen science must be incorporated to conserve species. It is the collection and analysis of data relating to the natural world by the city or country masses. It is typically a part of a collaborative effort with the professional scientists.

3

A plastic ban must be properly imposed. Plastic pollution is set to increase by 2050. Dumping of industrial and human waste into oceans is increasing the harmful effects on ecosystems.

- 4 Industrial discharge and effluent must be monitored.
- 5 Human and municipal waste must be treated before dumping.
- 6 Strict fine imposition on rule breakers.
- 7 Regulations on groundwater pumping so water tables do not decrease further, which are already getting low at alarming rates. by proper regulating measures, we can reduce the rate of destruction.

CASE STUDIES OF EFFECTIVE COASTAL UTILISATION

INDIA

India's extensive coastline, which is over 7,500 kilometers long, is greatly susceptible to the effects of climate change^[25]. The Indian Ocean is on whose bank most of India's major cities are located. A large coastline is good for trade and development from a point of view, but it can also be the cause of natural threats to the nation.

EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE:

Rising Sea Levels

Sea level rise is the most tangible impact of climate change, threatening low-lying coastal areas. For example, increased sea levels threaten cities such as Chennai, Kolkata, and Mumbai with flooding. Sea levels are likely to increase by 0.3 to 1 meter by 2100^[26], potentially swallowing precious land and displacing millions of people, says the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)^[27]. Wetland loss and coastal erosion exacerbate the problem.

Saltwater Intrusion

Drinking water supplies and agriculture are affected by saltwater intrusion into freshwater aquifers, resulting from sea level rise^[28]. For instance, saltwater intrusion has reduced yields for crops and degraded groundwater quality in Gujarat and West Bengal^[29]. This phenomenon is a major hindrance for farmers and surrounding communities that rely on freshwater sources^[30].

Cyclones and Extreme Weather

Cyclones on the Indian coast have grown more intensive and recurrent as a result of global warming. For example, Cyclone Amphan in 2020 ravaged West Bengal and Odisha, displacing millions of individuals and infrastructure^[31]. These events are made more destructive through the meeting of storm surges, heavy rains, and rising sea levels.

Loss of biodiversity

Climate change is jeopardizing coastal ecosystems, including mangroves, coral reefs, and wetlands. The Sundarbans, home to the Bengal tiger^[32], is a UNESCO World Heritage site particularly vulnerable to habitat loss and sea-level rise. The loss of these ecosystems affects both marine biodiversity and the livelihood of fishing communities.^[33]

POLICIES FOLLOWED BY THE GOVERNMENT OF INDIA:

Mangrove Restoration

India has recognized the role of mangroves in maintaining biodiversity and safeguarding the coast. The Sundarbans, shared by Bangladesh with the world's largest mangrove forest, acts as a natural defense system against tidal surges and cyclones. One such restoration activity is the Livelihoods-NEWS Project, which restored degraded land by planting more than 16 million mangrove plants, protecting communities and embankments from cyclones and other natural hazards like Cyclone Amphan in 2020^[33]. In addition, through sustainable aquaculture and ecotourism, The Nature Conservancy is restoring 100 hectares of mangroves in non-protected Sundarbans areas that enhance local livelihoods and ecological resilience.^[34]

Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ) Rules

In order to regulate development along the coast, the government has established CRZ regulations. India employs the Coastal Regulation Zone (CRZ) Rules, originally

promulgated in 1991 and amended in 2011 and 2019, to regulate development along its 7,500 km coastline. Under the rules, coastal areas are segmented into four zones (CRZ-I through CRZ-IV), each of which has specific restrictions. For example, whereas CRZ-II allows planned development in urban coastal areas, CRZ-I does not allow new buildings near ecologically fragile areas like mangroves and coral reefs^[35]. Along vulnerable regions, such as the Konkan Coast, these regulations have helped safeguard sensitive ecosystems.^[36]

Disaster Preparedness and Early Warning Systems

By investing in multi-hazard early warning systems, India has developed considerably in disaster preparedness. As much as 72 hours prior, the India Meteorological Department (IMD) provides impact-based cyclone forecasts with color-coded warnings^[37]. Cyclone deaths have reduced substantially due to this system. Specifically, the Director General of Meteorology, Dr. Mrutyunjay Mohapatra, was awarded for his pioneering efforts in this context^[38]. To present real-time alerts across the region, India is also part of the South Asia Flash Flood Guidance System.

International Commitments

India has updated its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) to make them more ambitious in terms of climate action and is a firm signatory to the Paris Agreement. These are achieving 50% of installed electricity generation from non-fossil fuel-based sources by 2030 and reducing the emissions intensity of the GDP by 45% below the base year of 2005^[39]. India also aims to go net-zero by 2070^[40]. India is addressing regional environmental challenges and aligning national actions with global climate objectives through initiatives such as the International Solar Alliance.

BANGLADESH:

Bangladesh's low-lying landscape and its closeness to the Bay of Bengal mean its coastal areas are especially exposed to climate change. Sea-level rise would flood extensive land areas, displacing millions of individuals and threatening crucial ecosystems like the Sundarbans mangrove forest. More frequent and intense cyclones raise the likelihood of flooding and destroying infrastructure. Additionally, water and agriculture supplies have been adversely affected by saltwater entry into freshwater resources, threatening the livelihood of coastal dwellers. Bangladesh is one of the most climate-vulnerable nations due to these conditions.

IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

Rising Sea Levels

Given that nearly two-thirds of its territory is less than 15 feet above sea level, Bangladesh faces a serious threat from rising sea levels. An estimated 11% of the nation's landmass may be under water by 2050, which could force more than 15 million people to relocate^[41]. The Sundarbans, the largest mangrove forest in the world and a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is especially at risk. According to a recent study using the Sea Level Affecting Marshes Model (SLAMM), 325 km² of Sundarbans land could be submerged under a scenario of 1 m sea level rise and 874 km² under a scenario of 2 m^[42]. In addition to destroying biodiversity, such an event would destroy the livelihoods of millions of people who rely on the forest for agriculture, fishing, and honey harvesting.

Increased Cyclones and Storm Surges

Cyclones in the Bay of Bengal have increased in frequency and intensity as a result of climate change. One of the most intense storms in the region's history was Cyclone Amphan, which hit land in May 2020. It displaced millions, destroyed critical infrastructure, and affected 10 million people across 19 districts in Bangladesh^[43]. Increasing sea levels have led to more frequent storm surges flooding coastal regions, destroying embankments and polluting freshwater resources. Locally based systems of resilience and disaster preparedness are under great pressure as a result of the increased unpredictability of these events.

Saltwater Intrusion

In Bangladesh's southwest coastal regions, such as Khulna, Satkhira, and Bagerhat, saltwater intrusion is becoming increasingly problematic. Groundwater and soil have been salinized due to increased sea level rise and reduced freshwater supply from the upstream rivers. Most farmers have been compelled to abandon rice farming in the traditional way due to this adverse effect on agriculture. For example, Satkhira farmers have turned to shrimp aquaculture, which can tolerate salty conditions but has led to loss of biodiversity, freshwater, and land degradation^[44]. Despite the fact that others have reverted to diversified farming, it is still challenging due to the prevailing salinity and water shortage.

Loss of Biodiversity

The loss of biodiversity is being enhanced by the degradation of coastal ecosystems, particularly the Sundarbans. The forest is home to estuarine crocodiles, hundreds of bird and fish species, and the Royal Bengal tiger. Nevertheless, most of these species,

are at risk of becoming extinct as a result of habitat fragmentation, sea level rise, and enhanced salinity. Climate change-induced sea level rise can result in the loss of Bengal tigers' habitable land in the Sundarbans by 2070, a study finds^[45]. Local fishing societies, which survive on the rich biodiversity of the forest both as an income source and for livelihood, are also affected by this ecological degradation^[46].

POLICIES FOLLOWED BY THE GOVERNMENT OF BANGLADESH:

Bangladesh has taken many proactive steps to counter the effects of climate change on its coastal region:

Bangladesh Change Strategy and Action Plan (BCCSAP)

The BCCSAP, originally presented in 2009 and revised in 2022, presents a holistic strategy to climate adaptation and mitigation^[47]. Among the actions proposed are the construction of cyclone shelters, enhancement of early warning systems, and climate-resilient agriculture. For example, multipurpose cyclone shelter construction has helped minimize casualties during severe weather conditions.

Delta Plan 2100

A 2100 long-term, visionary plan, the Bangladesh Delta Plan 2100 (BDP 2100), is focused on making sustainable development possible despite land degradation, water insecurity, and climate change^[48]. The BDP 2100 integrates climate resilience, environmental conservation, and economic advancement. It involves the construction and restoration of polders and embankments to protect lowlands from saltwater intrusion and tidal flooding. For example, to fund the improvement of drainage systems and embankment strengthening in susceptible regions such as the Ganges Delta, the World Bank has committed \$1.8 billion^[49]. Further, the strategy promotes adaptive delta management, which facilitates flexible responses to unexpected future climatic conditions^[50].

Community-Based Adaptation

Community-based adaptation, or CBA, is a bottom-up approach to climate resilience that Bangladesh has embraced. Women's organizations are also busy with the reforestation of mangroves on embankments along coastal areas like Satkhira and Khulna. The efforts provide alternative income opportunities besides guarding against storm surges. At Padmapukur village, for instance, the women collect and plant keora mangrove saplings, which they then use as input for making pickles and jams they sell^[51]. Thanks to the support of government forestry departments and non-governmental organizations such as Friendship, these initiatives have added over 100 acres of mangrove coverage and empowered over 1,500 women.

International Collaboration

Bangladesh actively participates in global climate actions and seeks other nations' help to aid its efforts at adaptation and mitigation. An example of this is that the country has sought funding from the Green Climate Fund to implement projects that enhance resilience among communities that are vulnerable^[52].

MALDIVES:

The Maldives experiences a tropical monsoon climate with warm temperatures and high humidity throughout the year. It has two seasons: the wet season (southwest monsoon) from May to October and the dry season (northeast monsoon) from November to April. The wet season is marked by heavy rain, powerful winds, and intermittent storms, while the dry season has clear skies and peaceful seas, ideal for tourism. The Maldives, being an island country, is also severely threatened by the rise in sea levels and changing weather patterns, placing it in a very sensitive position to climate change given its beautiful geography.

The low-lying nature of the Maldives, an island chain with over 1,100 coral islands, places it among the nations most vulnerable to climate change.

EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

Submerging Of Maldives

The Maldives is the world's lowest country and most exposed to sea level rise, standing on average at only 1 to 1.5 meters above sea level. Scientific estimates project

global warming continue, a maximum of 80% of the islands could become uninhabitable by 2050^[53]. For instance, beach erosion on the Dhiffushi Island has seen over 200 feet of shoreline disappear within recent years, while saltwater intrusion causes 10 to 20 coconut palms to die annually^[54]. Due to groundwater pollution, people currently have to depend almost solely on rainwater for drinking and flood twice monthly, compared to several times a year a decade ago.

Coral Bleaching

Aside from being biodiverse hotspots, the Maldivian coral reefs function as natural breakwaters, protecting the islands from storm surges. Nonetheless, mass bleaching has been caused by rising sea surface temperatures. One of the major bleaching incidents in 2016 affected over 60% of coral colonies, with up to 90% bleaching at certain places^[55]. El Niño and global warming triggered this event, which severely impaired reef structures, reducing their ability to absorb the energy of waves and support marine life. Restoration efforts are now under way by the Maldives Coral Institute and others, but recovery is doubtful and slow as a result of continuing warming.

Loss of Freshwater Resources

In the Maldives, freshwater shortages are becoming an increasingly significant issue. The islands depend on rain harvesting and shallow freshwater aquifers since they do not have rivers and lakes. But by 2021, 97% of inhabited islands will have groundwater that is unsuitable for human use because of saltwater intrusion caused by increased sea levels^[56]. People living in Dhiffushi and other islands currently survive on imported bottled water and rainwater tanks, which contributes to economic costs and plastic pollution^[57]. Rainwater harvesting systems^[57] have been promoted by the government and WHO but are not being used and serviced properly yet in most places^[58].

Rising Storm Surges and Flooding

Severe weather events, including storm surges, coastal flooding, and high-speed winds, are frequenting the Maldives. The World Bank estimates that 60% of resorts have suffered climate change-inflicted damage to infrastructure, and more than 90% indicate beach erosion^[59]. 36 surge-related events were reported by the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) alone in 2022, affecting hundreds of families and 62 islands^[60]. Besides threatening people and assets, the events also disrupt tourism, which forms the bulk of the Maldives' economy and accounts for 30% of GDP.

POLICIES FOLLOWED BY THE GOVERNMENT OF MALDIVES:

The Maldives has initiated proactive steps to counter the effects of climate change:

National Climate Action Plan

As the country's National Climate Action Plan, the Maldives has signed its Third Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to the Paris Agreement. With enough international support, this plan boldly commits to achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2030^[61]. The Maldives has pledged to reduce emissions by 26% by 2030 by implementing waste management reforms, clean transportation, and the growth of renewable energy, even though it emits only 0.003% of all global emissions^[62]. The plan also emphasizes adaptation actions such as the Climate Smart Resilient Islands Initiative, which integrates climate resilience in island development and was launched at the 2019 UN Climate Action Summit^[63].

Artificial Islands

The Maldives developed Hulhumalé, an artificial island reclaimed northeast of Malé, to address the threat of sea level rise. Built 2 meters above sea level, Hulhumalé is designed for up to 240,000 inhabitants with green areas, renewable energy infrastructure, and climate-resilient buildings^[64]. The project is designed to decongest Malé while providing communities affected by flooding and coastal erosion a safe refuge. Named the "City of Hope," Hulhumalé is one of the finest examples of sustainable urban planning for small island states^[65].

Coral Reef Restoration

The Maldives is home to some of the most biodiverse coral reefs on the planet, and they play critical roles in both tourism and coastal defense. Mass coral bleaching has seen active coral restoration programs, including mid-water rope nurseries and coral nurseries, undertaken by the government and non-governmental organizations to rehabilitate impacted reefs^[66]. The nation's largest reef rehabilitation project, the Rasfari Restoration Project, was initiated in 2023 and was facilitated by a \$10 million environmental settlement^[67]. These initiatives aim to enhance sustainable fishing, enhance biodiversity, and restore the health of reefs^[68].

International Advocacy

In light of the Alliance of Small Island States (AOSIS), the Maldives has been a vocal leader in international climate talks. President Ibrahim Mohamed Solih made a passionate argument at COP26 for rich nations to finance vulnerable countries such as the Maldives and honor their climate finance commitments^[69]. Maldives is

still advocating for the operationalization of the Loss and Damage Fund, which they co-established during COP27^[70]. Climate change is put at the forefront of the country's foreign policy as a global justice and survival issue^[71].

Community-based adaptation Action

Community-based adaptation is one of the most important results of the Maldives' approach to climate. To enhance local resilience, individuals in outer atolls are replenishing mangroves, collecting rainwater, and engaging in sustainable fishing^[72]. More than 100,000 individuals on 49 islands have integrated water supply systems as a result of activities like FP007, funded by the Green Climate Fund^[73]. This has reduced the demand for emergency water supplies during drought periods. Aside from meeting the water shortage, these projects empower communities, women in particular to take up leadership roles for environmental stewardship.

RECOMMENDATIONS

POLICY GAPS AND GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES IN PAKISTAN'S COASTAL MANAGEMENT:

While Pakistan has made initial strides in developing policies related to coastal governance, a number of critical weaknesses persist. These shortcomings limit the effectiveness of policy implementation and undermine efforts to build coastal resilience in the face of escalating environmental threats. Chief among these issues is the inadequate use of Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs). In many cases, development projects, particularly those near ecologically sensitive coastal zones, are launched without conducting proper EIAs. This oversight often results in irreversible damage to local ecosystems, loss of biodiversity, and increased vulnerability to natural disasters.

Another major gap is the limited integration of citizen science in environmental management practices. Citizen science, which involves the collection and analysis of environmental data by non-professional volunteers, has proven effective in conservation efforts globally. However, in Pakistan, it remains a largely unexplored and underutilized concept. By excluding local communities from scientific processes, valuable insights and collaborative opportunities for ecosystem monitoring and species conservation are lost.

In addition, Pakistan's ban on plastic use, although well-intentioned, suffers from weak implementation. Enforcement mechanisms are either absent or inconsistently applied, leading to a continued rise in plastic pollution. Without strong legal and institutional backing, the country is on track to witness a dramatic increase in plastic

waste by 2050. Compounding this issue is the unregulated discharge of industrial effluents into coastal waters. Many factories release untreated waste directly into the ocean, harming marine life and reducing water quality. Municipal waste systems fare no better; untreated human waste is frequently dumped into coastal zones, severely contaminating the marine environment and endangering public health.

Another area of concern is groundwater overextraction. In many coastal areas, groundwater levels have dropped to alarming lows due to unchecked pumping for agriculture, industry, and domestic use. Without regulatory oversight, this trend will continue to jeopardize water security. Additionally, the widespread use of single-use plastics remains a pressing issue. These items not only contribute to terrestrial and marine pollution but also place a significant burden on the country's already weak waste management infrastructure.

Recommendations for Improved Coastal Governance and Resilience in Pakistan:

To address these challenges, Pakistan must adopt a multifaceted approach that prioritizes both ecological integrity and community engagement. First and foremost, environmental impact assessments must be made mandatory and conducted with full transparency. The EIA process should include stakeholder consultations, thorough environmental assessments, impact forecasting, and long-term monitoring. These steps are essential in ensuring that new development projects do not compromise environmental sustainability.

fig. Steps of the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Process

Secondly, Pakistan should integrate citizen science into its conservation strategies. Encouraging public participation in environmental monitoring fosters a sense of ownership and empowers communities to take part in decision-making processes. Such collaboration between citizens and scientists can significantly enhance the accuracy and scope of ecological data collection.

The Role of Citizen Science in Conservation

fig. Role of Citizen Science in Species Conservation

Thirdly, the plastic ban must be enforced rigorously. Regulatory authorities need to ensure compliance through regular inspections, penalties for violations, and support for industries transitioning to biodegradable alternatives. Public awareness campaigns can also play a vital role in reducing plastic consumption. If left unchecked, plastic pollution is projected to increase drastically by mid-century.

Effective Plastic Ban Implementation

Furthermore, the discharge of industrial effluents should be closely monitored. Industries must be required to treat wastewater before disposal, and independent audits should be mandated to ensure compliance with environmental standards. Similarly, municipal authorities must upgrade waste treatment facilities to prevent the release of untreated sewage into the ocean.

The imposition of fines on environmental violations, coupled with incentives for eco-friendly practices, can significantly improve regulatory adherence. Meanwhile, the extraction of groundwater must be controlled through a system of permits, usage caps, and recharge initiatives. By managing this resource more sustainably, Pakistan can prevent further depletion of its vital aquifers.

Lastly, a complete ban on single-use plastic items should be enforced nationwide. These products are among the leading contributors to solid waste pollution and must be replaced with reusable and biodegradable alternatives. Combined, these measures can greatly improve coastal governance, build community resilience, and promote long-term ecological balance.

CONCLUSION

Pakistan's coastline stands at a critical juncture, where the accelerating impacts of climate change demand urgent and coordinated action. The threats of sea level rise, erosion, coral reef degradation, and socio-economic disruption are no longer future risks, they are unfolding realities that endanger both human lives and ecological integrity.

This report has highlighted not only the environmental and economic vulnerabilities of Pakistan's coastal regions but also the gaps in governance, policy implementation, and public engagement. While promising initiatives such as mangrove restoration, the Blue Carbon Project, and the National Climate Change Policy have been introduced, their impact remains limited without robust enforcement and community involvement.

To build true coastal resilience, Pakistan must adopt a multi-layered strategy that integrates scientific research, local knowledge, and regional cooperation. Strengthening institutional frameworks, promoting sustainable development, and empowering coastal communities are essential steps toward mitigating the looming crisis.

Protecting our coastlines is not just an environmental obligation—it is a national imperative that intersects with food security, economic stability, and long-term sustainability. The time to act is now.

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